

SOME ISSUES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS ON ACCOUNTABILITY FOR VIOLATIONS OF JUDICIAL ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS IN THE LEGISLATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyzes the issue of accountability for violations of judicial ethical standards from the perspective of international norms and examines how these standards are reflected in the national legislation of Uzbekistan. It evaluates the alignment between the recommendations of international bodies such as the United Nations and the Council of Europe and the national legal framework aimed at ensuring the independence, impartiality, and responsibility of judges. Particular attention is paid to the existing mechanisms of accountability for breaches of judicial ethics, their effectiveness, and compliance with international practices. The author puts forward proposals and recommendations for reforming this area, incorporating international experience, and improving national legislation.

Keywords: judicial ethics, international standards, accountability, legislative implementation, judicial independence, fair trial

A judge must adhere to certain moral standards not only during the exercise of their professional duties related to the administration of justice but also in their daily life outside of professional activity. Observance of the rules of judicial ethics should not stem from obligation alone, but rather naturally arise from the judge's high moral, educational, and ethical upbringing. Every judge is required to comply with the relevant code of professional conduct both in their official duties and in

their behavior outside of those duties. Failure to observe these ethical rules may lead to disciplinary or other forms of liability, which is established as an international legal standard.

In particular, according to the **Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct**, these principles are intended to serve as a guide for judges and as fundamental standards for judicial bodies in determining appropriate conduct. Judges are accountable to independent and impartial bodies that support and uphold judicial ethics not with the aim of diminishing the importance of existing norms and rules, but rather to strengthen them. Based on Indicator 4 of the Bangalore Principles, adherence to ethical norms and demonstrating such adherence is considered an integral part of judicial activity.

The ultimate goal of the judicial and legal reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to strengthen judicial independence and to transform the judiciary into a true guardian of legality and justice. As emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev:

“Let me reiterate once again: in the mind of a judge there must be justice, on the tongue — truth, and in the heart — purity.”

In this regard, the words of our great ancestor Alisher Navoi carry deep meaning:

“Do not commit injustice, be fair, and build a 'fortress of justice' for the people.”

When does this “fortress of justice” emerge? It can only be achieved when judicial bodies and judges strictly adhere to the law and the principles of fairness, fulfilling their duties honestly and conscientiously.

While the majority of representatives of the judiciary in Uzbekistan comply with the norms of professional ethics, cases of disciplinary liability for unethical behavior by judges occur in every country. According to information provided by the **Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan**, in 2023 alone, a

total of **720 disciplinary cases** (472 in 2022) were initiated. As a result:

- **369 judges** were subjected to disciplinary sanctions;
- The judicial powers of **29 judges** (22 in 2022) were terminated prematurely;
- **126 judges** (103) received reprimands;
- **23 judges** (16) were fined;
- **191 judges** (132) received official warnings;
- In **344 cases** (196), disciplinary proceedings were terminated;
- In **2 cases**, disciplinary cases were canceled.

The initiated disciplinary cases were distributed as follows:

- **324** (217) involved civil court judges,
- **285** (200) criminal court judges,
- **75** (40) economic court judges, and
- **36** (15) administrative court judges.

As a subject of international law, the Republic of Uzbekistan has incorporated relevant international standards concerning the judiciary and the status of judges into its national legislation. These include norms on holding judges accountable for violations of laws and ethical rules both in the course of administering justice and in their conduct outside of professional activity.

Indeed, the high status and broad powers granted to the judiciary and judges require that members of the judicial corps demonstrate a high degree of responsibility, humility, and restraint. They are expected to resolve cases strictly based on the law, impartiality, and justice. Otherwise, judges found guilty of misconduct are subject to disciplinary liability as established by both international and national legal frameworks.

International standards emphasize that the institution of disciplinary liability for judges must not compromise their independence or inviolability. In particular, **Article 11 of the Universal Charter of the Judge** stipulates that the administration

of the judicial system and the initiation of disciplinary proceedings against judges must be organized in such a way that judicial independence is never called into question. Only impartial and essential factors should be taken into account in such processes.

If no other procedures derived from time-tested traditions are in place, the management of the judicial system and the initiation of disciplinary proceedings against judges must be carried out by an independent body in which judges constitute the majority.

Disciplinary proceedings against a judge may only be initiated in accordance with procedural norms provided for and established in the applicable legislation, ensuring appropriate safeguards.

According to **Article 5.1 of the European Charter on the Statute for Judges**, failure by a judge to fulfill the specific duties inherent in their judicial office may result in the imposition of disciplinary measures **only** following a procedure based on a judicial decision or a decision, recommendation, or approval made by a body in which at least half of the members are elected judges. The proceedings must be adversarial in nature, and the judge subject to disciplinary action must have access to legal representation.

The types of sanctions applied are determined by the judicial statute, and their application must comply with the **principle of proportionality**.

Furthermore, under this provision, any decision rendered by an executive authority, judicial body, or other institution imposing a disciplinary sanction may be appealed to a higher judicial instance.

These international standards have been implemented into the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account not only advanced global models but also national traditions and accumulated experience in organizing the judicial system. In particular, according to **Article 74 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts”** (hereinafter referred to as “the Law on Courts”),

disciplinary measures against a judge may only be applied based on a decision of the relevant Qualification Board of Judges. Such disciplinary liability may be imposed if a judge:

- violates the law in the course of administering justice,
- demonstrates negligence or misconduct in organizing judicial proceedings,
- commits acts that tarnish the honor and dignity of a judge or undermine the authority of the court, or
- breaches the requirements of the **Code of Judicial Ethics**.

In accordance with this law, disciplinary proceedings against a judge may be initiated by the relevant Qualification Board of Judges based on the results of an internal investigation conducted in response to a complaint or report regarding the judge's conduct that may serve as grounds for disciplinary liability.

If it is confirmed during the disciplinary process that the judge has indeed committed acts warranting liability, the following disciplinary sanctions may be applied:

- a **warning**,
- a **reprimand**,
- a **fine** of no more than thirty percent of the judge's average monthly salary,
- **lowering of the qualification grade by one level**, or
- **early termination of judicial powers**.

A disciplinary case against a judge may be initiated by the Chairperson of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan through a formal decision. This decision must clearly state the grounds for initiating disciplinary proceedings.

It should be noted that, according to **Article 74 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Courts"**, a judge may be held disciplinarily liable **only** based on a decision by the relevant Judicial Qualification Board and **only in the following**

cases:

- for violating the law during the administration of justice;
- for negligence or misconduct in organizing court proceedings resulting in procedural deficiencies;
- for committing actions that tarnish the honor and dignity of a judge or undermine the reputation of the court;
- for violating the requirements of the **Code of Judicial Ethics**.

Experts have pointed out that the legislation does not provide clear definitions or criteria as to **what specific actions** constitute violations of the law in the administration of justice, or **how** negligence and misconduct in court management should be assessed for the purposes of imposing disciplinary liability. Furthermore, there are **no internal regulations or procedural guidelines** that clearly govern this matter.

This legal ambiguity creates a risk of **misinterpretation** of Article 74 of the Law "On Courts" by Judicial Qualification Boards during disciplinary proceedings, as well as the **inconsistent evaluation** of misconduct, potentially leading to unequal application of disciplinary measures against judges.

Article 12.1 of the Federal Law of the Russian Federation No. 179-FZ dated July 2, 2013, "On the Status of Judges in the Russian Federation" provides a clear definition of the concept of judicial disciplinary liability. According to this article, **disciplinary liability** refers to the commission of a culpable act or omission by a judge, either during the performance of official duties or outside of official capacity, which results in a violation of the provisions of this law or the Code of Judicial Ethics, thereby tarnishing the honor and dignity of the judicial office and undermining the authority of the judiciary.

In order to deepen the process of implementing international legal standards concerning the status of judges into the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to improve the institutional framework for judicial disciplinary liability, it is

considered necessary to **legally clarify** and enhance the regulatory framework. This includes amending relevant legal acts such as the **Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Courts"** and the **Regulation "On Judicial Qualification Boards"** to include clear definitions of:

- the concept, elements, and characteristics of disciplinary liability,
- the time limits for initiating disciplinary proceedings, and
- the legal mechanisms for imposing disciplinary sanctions on judges.

Such legal clarity would ensure a more structured, transparent, and fair disciplinary process within the judiciary.

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